

Distribution and ecology of *Mercuria tachoensis* (Gastropoda: Hydrobiidae) in Portugal and evidence that *M. edmundi* is conspecific

Distribución y ecología de *Mercuria tachoensis* (Gastropoda: Hydrobiidae) en Portugal y evidencia de que *M. edmundi* es coespecífica

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ABSTRACT

Distribution and ecology of *Mercuria* in Portugal are reviewed. *M. tachoensis* was still found present over much of the range recorded historically in the lowlands of W. Portugal. Our recent records are almost all of it living in small streams with clean water close to spring-heads (26 of 28 localities), with none from the larger rivers in W. Portugal. However, a site in the R. Guadiana in Baixo Alentejo had living snails on mud exposed where fresh or slightly saline river water had fallen during low tides. Since its original description in 1986, *M. edmundi* has been differentiated from *M. tachoensis* only on the basis of larger shell size, presence of a large rounded bulge on the penial appendage and shorter penis relative to length of the appendage. We demonstrate that size of the penial appendage is correlated with shell size; both apparently increase seasonally from November to May. Also, intermediates are frequent, and there is no consistent correlation of penis length with development of the appendage. Hence it is inferred that the type material of *M. edmundi* was of *M. tachoensis* approaching sexual maturity, with shells approaching full size, so the name should be regarded as a taxonomic synonym of the latter.

RESUMEN

Se revisan la distribución y la ecología de *Mercuria* en Portugal. *Mercuria tachoensis* todavía se encontró presente en gran parte del área registrada históricamente en las tierras bajas del Oeste de Portugal. Nuestros registros recientes son casi todos de ejemplares viviendo en pequeños arroyos con agua limpia cerca de los manantiales (26 de 28 localidades), ninguno de los ríos más grandes del Oeste de Portugal. Sin embargo, un sitio en el Río Guadiana en el Baixo Alentejo tenía caracoles vivos en el fango expuesto donde el agua dulce o ligeramente salobre del río había caído durante la bajamar. Desde su descripción original en 1986, *M. edmundi* se ha diferenciado de *M. tachoensis* tan sólo sobre la base de un mayor tamaño de la concha, la presencia de una gran protuberancia redondeada en el apéndice peniano y el pene más corto con relación a la longitud del apéndice. Demostramos en tres de seis poblaciones estudiadas que el tamaño del apéndice peniano está correlacionado con el tamaño de la concha; ambos parecen aumentar estacionalmente de noviembre a mayo. Además, los intermedios son frecuentes, y no hay correlación consistente de la longitud del pene con el desarrollo del apéndice. Por lo tanto se infiere que el material tipo de *M. edmundi* era de *M. tachoensis* acercándose a la madurez sexual, con las conchas acercándose al tamaño definitivo, por lo que el nombre debe ser considerado como un sinónimo taxonómico de este último.

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INTRODUCTION

Studies of Iberian Hydrobiidae by BOETERS (1986, 1988) reported both *Mercuria tachoensis* (Frauenfeld, 1865) and the newly described *M. edmundi* Boeters, 1986 from Portugal, giving five localities for the former and three for the latter species. However, older literature described the same small freshwater snails as much more widely distributed: MORELET (1845: 91) noting *Paludina similis* Michaud as “extrêmement multipliée dans toutes les eaux du Portugal méridional, est particulièrement abondante dans celles qui arrosent la vallée du Tage”. NOBRE (1941: 211-213) listed numerous localities; these and additional more recent records were mapped by MATOS (2014: 45-46). ROLÁN & OLIVEIRA (2007) confirmed the occurrence of *M. tachoensis* further north at Porto.

The original description of *M. edmundi* differentiated it from *M. tachoensis* on the basis of three characters: larger shell size (height 3.0-3.5 mm, cf. up to 2.9 mm; breadth >1.5 mm cf. <1.5 mm), the presence of a large rounded bulge on the penial appendage that is absent or indistinct in *M. tachoensis*, and penis length about equal to that of the appendage whereas it is longer than the appendage in *M. tachoensis* (BOETERS, 1986: 126-127, 1988: 207-211; repeated in GLOER ET AL., 2015). Unfortunately, the account by MATOS (2014: 45-47) reversed the shell size characters used to define the two taxa. However, our initial attempts to identify Portuguese specimens disclosed a considerable proportion of snails in which the three characters were not correlated, others in which the shape of the penial appendage was intermediate, as well as variability within populations.

This paper provides a summary of recent distributional records of *Mercuria* in continental Portugal, comments on the ecology and habitat preferences and reconsiders the taxonomic status of *M. edmundi* based on study of larger samples from more localities.

DISTRIBUTION AND ECOLOGY

During 2007-2016 recording by Álvaro de Oliveira and our own studies showed that *M. tachoensis* was still present over much of the range recorded historically in the lowlands of western Portugal, with a new record also in SE. Baixo Alentejo (Fig. 1).

MORELET (1845: 91) reported “on la trouve indifféremment dans les eaux vives et dans les marécages” with a record also from the “fontaine du couvent d’Arrábida”. Our recent finds are all from low ground (near sea level up to ca 270 m altitude) and almost all from regions with calcareous rocks, mainly of Mesozoic age. It apparently avoids the uplands of most of northern and eastern Portugal with their predominance of hard Palaeozoic rocks and soft water. Almost all of our records are of it living in small streams with clean clear water at or close to spring-heads arising from limestone (26 localities), with one of old shells from a muddy stream near a spring in Ribatejo. Our living *Mercuria* were sometimes associated with living *Belgrandia* spp., *Theodoxus* cf. *fluviatilis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Potamopyrgus antipodarum* (J.E. Gray, 1843), *Physa acuta* Draparnaud, 1805, *Ancylus fluviatilis* O.F. Müller, 1774, *Radix* cf. *baltica* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Galba truncatula* (O.F. Müller, 1774), *Bithynia tentaculata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Planorbarius metidjensis* (Forbes, 1838) and *Ferrissia fragilis* (Tryon, 1863); there were single records also with *Corbicula fluminea* O.F. Müller, 1774 and (nearby but in deeper water) *Unio delphinus* Spengler, 1793 (both in R. Guadiana). None were found by us in the larger rivers of western Portugal, probably suggesting a pattern of local extinctions there as with other freshwater prosobranchs such as *Bithynia tentaculata* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Valvata piscinalis* (O.F. Müller, 1774) (cf. maps in MATOS, 2014: 36, 56), likely to have been caused by eutrophication, other pollution, and effects of water abstraction.

The newly discovered site in Baixo Alentejo (in Rio Guadiana ca 1 km W. of Pomarão, UTM 29S 0629 / 4157) was radically different, the live snails being co-

Figure 1. Distribution of *Mercuria* in continental Portugal mapped by 10 km squares of the U.T.M. grid. Filled circles show the authors' records 2012-2016 and records made by Álvaro de Oliveira from 2007-2009; open circles show records from before 2005, mainly from the literature. *Figura 1. Distribución de Mercuria en Portugal continental, mapeada por cuadrados de 10 km de la cuadrícula U.T.M.. Los círculos llenos muestran los registros de los autores de 2012-2016 y los registros realizados por Álvaro de Oliveira de 2007-2009. Los círculos abiertos muestran registros de antes de 2005, principalmente a partir de la literatura.*

llected from the surface of mud exposed when the fresh or slightly saline water of this river was at its twice-daily low level caused by tidal influence (near the upstream tidal limit). The habitat there was thus similar to the remarkably specialised habitat of *M. anatina* (Poiret, 1801) (synonyms *M. confusa* auct., *M. similis* auct.: cf. BOETERS & FALKNER, 2000; FALKNER, RIPKEN & FALKNER, 2002: 77; ANDERSON, 2005: 624; BOETERS & FALKNER, 2017: 239) in Britain and Ireland (OLDHAM, 1922; HOLYOAK, 1983; KERNY, 1999: 35). However, careful comparisons of the R. Guadiana specimens show they are typical of *M. tachoensis*, resembling other Portuguese material, and differing from British and Irish *M.*

anatina (in Collection of G.A.H.) in the narrower shell resulting from the body whorl not being disproportionately larger than the penultimate whorl.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Samples were collected from several different *Mercuria* populations during 2012-2014 and studied systematically in an attempt to clarify the relationship between the characters supposed to differentiate *M. edmundi* from *M. tachoensis*. Large populations that could withstand collection of many snails were chosen, with samples taken at different seasons of the year (see Table I). The snails were

Table I. Data on samples of *Mercuria* from Portugal. The samples are listed in order of month and day of collecting from November onwards in order to demonstrate an apparent pattern of seasonal change. Data listed give ranges of measurements of shell height (h), length of free part of penis (fp), ratio of greatest breadth to greatest length of penial appendage (ab/al), and ratio fp/al. The "Results" column give counts of dissected males showing supposed penis characters resembling *M. edmundi* (e), *M. tachoensis* (t), or intermediate (i), on basis of ab/al ratios (see text); those with representative examples shown in Fig. 2 are marked with an asterisk*. All material is preserved in collection of G.A. and D.T. Holyoak.

*Tabla I. Datos sobre muestras de Mercuria procedentes de Portugal. Las muestras se enumeran en orden de mes y día de recolección, a partir de noviembre, para demostrar un patrón aparente de cambio estacional. Los datos enumerados dan rangos de medidas de la altura de la concha (h), longitud de la parte libre del pene (fp), proporción entre la mayor anchura y la mayor longitud del apéndice peniano (ab/al) y relación fp/al. La columna "Results" da un recuento de machos disecados mostrando supuestos caracteres de pene parecidos a *M. edmundi* (e), *M. tachoensis* (t), o intermedio (i); aquellos con ejemplares representativos en la Fig. 2 están marcados con un asterisco*. Todo el material se conserva en la colección de G.A. y D. T. Holyoak.*

Site reference	Locality name	UTM coordinates	Date	Results
P344 Data: h 2.0-2.9 mm, fp 0.48-0.81 mm, fp/al 0.82-1.11, ab/al 0.26-0.37	Nascente da Moura, Alpedriz	29S 050360/438653	9 Nov. 2013	- 1i* 3t*
P232 Data: h 2.8-3.1 mm, fp 0.44-0.71 mm, fp/al 0.74-1.17, ab/al 0.27-0.48	Fonte dos Amores, Coimbra	29T 054807/444979	29 Feb. 2012	1e 2i 2t
P351B Data: h 2.4-3.2 mm, fp 0.49-0.73 mm, fp/al 0.63-1.33, ab/al 0.36-0.54	Nascente do Senhor Jordão, Alpedriz	29S 050357/438649	5 Mar. 2014	2e* 4i* -
P355 Data: h 3.3-3.6 mm, fp 0.53-0.72 mm, fp/al 0.88-1.22, ab/al 0.44-0.51	Fonte dos Amores, Coimbra	29T 054806/444981	15 Mar. 2014	2e 2i -
P382 Data: h 3.7, 4.0 mm, fp 0.60, 0.72 mm, fp/al 0.76, 1.07, ab/al 0.50, 0.53	Rio Guadiana, Pomarão	29S 0629/4157	18 Apr. 2014	2e - -
RdMF Data: h 3.6-3.9 mm, fp 0.48-0.57 mm, fp/al 0.71-1.15, ab/al 0.52-0.64	Ribeira de Maciel Forro, Mafra	29S 047060/430859	27 Apr. 2013	3e - -
FdP Data: h 3.3-4.0 mm, fp 0.39-0.71 mm, fp/al 0.42-0.98, ab/al 0.49-0.78	Fonte dos Passarinhos, Matacães	29S 48174/43269	25 May 2013	5e* - -

collected using sieves or hand-picked from stones and leaves. They were killed by immersion in 80% industrial methylated spirit (i.m.s.) in which they were preserved. Although the snails were often narcotised using menthol crystals, they invariably had the forepart of the body withdrawn into the shell aperture beneath the mantle collar when preserved, so that dissection was necessary to study the external penis in detail.

Subsequent dissection and observations were made using Meiji RZ series stereomicroscopes at magnifications of

up to $\times 56$, with intense illumination from a Schott KL 1500 light source via twin fibre-optic swan necks. The shell of each specimen being studied was supported on Blu Tack® Reusable Adhesive, in which small depressions were filled with 80% i.m.s. to prevent the soft body drying during manipulation and observation. Shells of adults could not be distinguished consistently from those of immatures, so subsamples comprising most of the medium-sized and large shells were picked at random for detailed study. The shell height was measu-

red using an eyepiece micrometer as the maximum from the top of the protoconch to the lowest part of the outer basal edge of the peristome. The shell was then broken away piece by piece with fine forceps, working backwards from the aperture to expose the mantle. The mantle collar was cut along the dorsal midline allowing the mantle to be pulled back to expose the dorsal surface of the forepart of the body, where the external penis is obvious in male specimens, which formed about half of all those examined. Drawings of the penis and penial appendix were made using a Meiji drawing tube and measurements were made from the drawings. The penis of a few specimens was broken during removal of the shell or subsequent dissection, leaving 29 useful (i.e. undamaged) male specimens from seven samples (six localities) that were studied (Table I), all of them being drawn (eleven representative specimens being shown in Fig. 2). Figure 3 shows relationships between shell height, length of the free part of the penis and the greatest breadth and length of the penial appendage.

RESULTS

There was no correlation of the length of the free penis with shell size (Fig. 3A) or with the length of the penial appendage (Fig. 3C), so these characters appear to have no value in discrimination of *M. edmundi* from *M. tachoensis*. The ratio of penial appendage breadth to length (ab/al) was found to increase with increasing shell size, at least for shell heights above 2.5 mm (Fig. 3B). Ratios of $ab/al > \text{ or } = \text{ to } 0.45$ would appear to characterise *M. edmundi*, whereas those $< \text{ or } = \text{ to } 0.35$ characterise *M. tachoensis* (cf. BOETERS, 1986, 1988). On that basis, our 29 specimens would appear to be comprised of 15 *M. edmundi*, 5 *M. tachoensis*, and 9 intermediate individuals (31 %) (Fig. 3B, Table I).

Furthermore, the samples showed penial anatomy clearly conforming to that described for *M. edmundi* in some snails from five of the six localities we

studied in detail. Three intermediates possibly matching the penial anatomy of *M. edmundi* were found at the sixth locality (P344). In our samples, specimens with smaller shells and the penis anatomy of *M. tachoensis* were found at two of the localities (P232, P344). This predominance of the "very rare" *M. edmundi* was surprising because it had hitherto only ever been confirmed anatomically from three locations which were all different to those involved here. Our site P232 (Fonte dos Amores at Quinta das Lágrimas) produced individuals collected from within a metre of each other on 29 Feb. 2012 with penial anatomy matching both *M. edmundi* (1) and *M. tachoensis* (2) along with intermediates (2), whereas BOETERS (1988: 207) reported only *M. tachoensis* there. Moreover, BOETERS (1988: 209-211) himself noted the apparent sympatry of *M. edmundi* and *M. tachoensis* at his "Jardim Botânico Lisboa" locality, one of only three from which the former taxon was reported. However, the frequent occurrence of intermediate degrees of development of the penial appendage and the lack of correlation of relative penis and appendage length with shell size found by us must make it doubtful that our samples contained two valid species.

A theoretical possibility that there are two species which are often sympatric and which occupy different microfacies and mature at different seasons receives no support from our observations. Indeed, it seems unlikely in view of the really tiny extent, just a few square metres, of several water bodies we sampled (e.g. P344, P232/355, P351B).

In our material, judging from the relative size of shells and of the penial appendage (Figs 2, 3B, Table I), the proportion of "*M. edmundi*" in each sample apparently increased from late autumn to early spring, so that no "*M. tachoensis*" were found in April or May. Thus, intermediates or "*M. tachoensis*" predominated in a sample collected on 9 November 2013 (at P344), "*M. edmundi*" (2) and intermediates (4) were present on 5 March 2014 (at P351B, only 50 m away), whe-

Figure 2. Drawings of the penis and penial appendage of representative specimens of *Mercuria* from Portugal. Areas of grey pigmentation on the penis are stippled. The drawings are arranged in ascending sequence according to shell height (h); the dates of collection and site references are given alongside the figures to which they apply (see Table I for other details).

Figura 2. Dibujos del pene y del apéndice peniano de especímenes representativos de *Mercuria* procedentes de Portugal. Áreas de pigmentación gris en el pene son punteadas. Los dibujos están dispuestos en orden ascendente según la altura (h) de la concha; Las fechas de recogida y las referencias del sitio se dan junto con las figuras a las que se aplican (ver Tabla I para otros detalles).

Figure 3. Scatter diagrams showing relationships between shell size and features of the male genitalia in 29 specimens of *Mercuria* from Portugal listed in Table I: A shell height (h) and length of free part of penis (fp); B shell height and ratio of greatest breadth to greatest length of penial appendage (ab/al); C shell height and ratio of length of free part of penis and greatest length of penial appendage (fp/al). In B, dashed lines separate samples with penial anatomy conforming to that of “*M. edmundi*” (e), *M. tachoensis* (t), and intermediates (i).

Figura 3. Diagramas de dispersion que muestran las relaciones entre el tamaño de la concha y las características de los genitales masculinos en 29 ejemplares de *Mercuria* de Portugal enumerados en la Tabla I: A altura de la concha (h) y longitud de la parte libre del pene (fp); B altura de la concha y relación entre la mayor anchura y la mayor longitud del apéndice peniano (ab/al); C altura de la concha y la relación entre la longitud de la parte libre del pene y la mayor longitud del apéndice peniano (fp/al). En B, las líneas discontinuas separan las muestras con anatomía peniana conforme a la de “*M. edmundi*” (e), *M. tachoensis* (t), y intermedios (i).

reas only “*M. edmundi*” was found later in the spring on 18 April 2014 (P382), 27 April 2013 (RdMF) and 25th May 2013 (FdP). While it is plausible that there could be two species maturing at different seasons, the evidence these may co-exist in tiny water bodies (P232/355) would not be expected, and the occurrence of intermediate degrees of development of the penial appendage in four samples from three sites suggests other explanations are much more likely. Instead, a more parsimonious explanation is that the “*M. tachoensis*” changed progressively into “*M. edmundi*” as they matured and grew larger shells from late autumn through the winter to late

spring. It appears that the penis commonly attains its full length but remains slender during several months before the penial appendage increases in size and the basal part of the penis becomes wider (Fig. 2). Dark (grey) pigmentation on the penis extends to a variable extent onto the most closely adjacent areas of the appendage, but a few individuals completely lack dark penial pigmentation. We must infer that the type material of *M. edmundi* (penis figured by BOETERS, 1986: 126 figs 4, 6) was of *M. tachoensis* approaching sexual maturity, with shells approaching full size (height 3.0-3.5 mm), so the name should be regarded as a taxonomic synonym of the latter.

DISCUSSION

If other taxa in the genus *Mercuria* show comparable allometric growth of the penis and penial appendage, or they are similar in having rather large distal male genitalia before the shells reach full size, there appears to be potential for error in naming new species based on unique samples from isolated localities. At present, some authors recognise numerous subtly different and mainly allopatric *Mercuria* species (e.g. FALKNER ET AL., 2002; GLOER ET AL., 2015) whereas others have suggested there is only one variable species in the Mediterranean region (e.g. GIUSTI, 1979; ANDERSON, 2005: 624). Hence, in addition to more morphological studies, a molecular-phylogenetic analysis of nominal taxa from

throughout the range of the genus is desirable to add to the body of data available for judging species limits. This would allow more realistic consideration of possible conservation concerns with *Mercuria*. Nevertheless, the work by WHELAN & STRONG (2015) suggests particular caution is needed in using data from mitochondrial DNA of spring snails since their study showed “extreme incongruence” with the anatomical and life-history information.

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